

Prevalence of healthcare-associated infections and its relationship with health determinants in ICU patients from the José Carrasco Arteaga hospital

Prevalencia de las infecciones asociadas a la atención en salud y su relación con determinantes de la salud en pacientes de las UCI del hospital José Carrasco Arteaga

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Abstract

Background: Health care-associated infections (HAI) represent a public health care problem and are defined as infections that appear within the first 48 hours of hospitalization or within 30 days after receiving medical care.

Objective: To determine the prevalence of HAI and its relationship with determinants of health on intensive care unit (ICU) patients of the José Carrasco Arteaga Hospital in the year 2019. **Materials and Methods:** An analytical study was performed with the medical records of 515 patients treated in 2019 in the ICU of the José Carrasco Arteaga Hospital. Simple and double entry tables were used, as well as a significance level of 95% ($p < 0.05$) to measure the relationship between the presence of HAI and the determinants of health. **Results:** Older adults (47.4%) predominated in the study population, with 53% being male, especially residing in urban areas (70.3%). The most common comorbidities were hypertension,

diabetes and cancer. The majority used medical devices in their treatment (74%), with hospital stays of 3-6 days (76.3%). HAI were caused by bacteria such as *Escherichia coli* 25%, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* 12.7% and *Staphylococcus spp* 27%; as well as fungi like *Candida glabrata* with 2.5%. There was a significant relationship between in-hospital factors and HAI, whereas there was no significant link with out-of-hospital factors. **Conclusions:** The prevalence of HAI was 15,3 per 100 patients. In-hospital factors were the most important, especially prolonged stay and the use of medical devices, mainly mechanical ventilation and bladder catheter.

Keywords: Health care-associated infections, health determinants, microorganisms, intensive care unit, infections.

Antecedentes: Las infecciones asociadas a la atención de la salud IAAS, representan un problema de salud público, aparecen por primera vez 48 horas o más después de la hospitalización o dentro de los 30 días después de haber recibido atención médica. **Objetivo:** Determinar la prevalencia de las IAAS y su relación con determinantes de la salud en pacientes de las UCIs del Hospital José Carrasco Arteaga del IESS, en el año 2019. **Materiales y métodos:** Se realizó un estudio analítico con las historias clínicas de 515 pacientes atendidos en 2019 en UCIs del Hospital José Carrasco Arteaga. Se emplearon tablas simples y de doble entrada, con un nivel de significancia del 95% ($p < 0.05$) para medir la relación entre la presencia de IAAS y los determinantes de la salud. **Resultados:** Predominaron los adultos mayores (47.4%), con un 53% masculinos, residentes preferentemente en zonas urbanas (70.3%). Las comorbilidades más comunes fueron HTA, diabetes y cáncer. La mayoría tuvo uso de dispositivos médicos en su tratamiento (74%), con estancias hospitalarias de 3 a 6 días (76.3%). Las IAAS fueron causadas tanto por bacterias: Gram negativas: *Escherichia coli* 25%, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* 12.7% y Gram positivas: *Staphylococcus spp* 27%. El hongo más frecuente fue *Candida glabrata* con 2.5%. Hubo relación significativa entre los factores intrahospitalarios y las IAAS, no así con los extra-hospitalarios. **Conclusiones:** La prevalencia de IAAS fue de 15.3 por cada 100 pacientes. Los factores intrahospitalarios fueron los más importantes, sobre todo la estadía prolongada y el uso de dispositivos médicos, principalmente ventilación mecánica y sonda vesical.

Palabras clave: Infecciones asociadas a la asistencia sanitaria, determinantes de la salud, microorganismos, Unidad de Cuidados Intensivos, infecciones.

tients, underscoring the profound impact of this issue in public healthcare^{6,7}.

On the other hand, health determinants are a group of factors that include social, economic, and environmental variables that influence the state of health of individuals and populations⁸. These factors, ranging from water quality in healthcare facilities to the educational level of medical personnel, influence patients' vulnerability to complications. For instance, HAI are usually driven by prolonged use of mechanical ventilation, catheters, and other invasive devices. Moreover, healthcare institutions are frequently colonized with multidrug-resistant organisms worsening the outcomes of HAI^{2,9}. Understanding which factors contribute the most to the prevalence of HAI is critical for developing effective preventive measures in vulnerable populations.

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), one of every twenty in-hospital patients will acquire a HAI. These estimations amount to nearly 4 million patients per year in the European Union and 2 million in the United States alone¹⁰. Given the significant epidemiological and financial burden, analyzing health determinants is imperative, not only to identify risk factors but also to foster the development of well-founded management and prevention protocols. Understanding the underlying mechanisms driving these infections allows for appropriate measures to be implemented; thus, reducing the associated morbidity and mortality, while also alleviating the financial burden of extended hospital stays and intensive treatments. This study aims to provide insights into the epidemiology of HAI in the José Carrasco Arteaga Hospital to enhance infection control policies and preventive measures.

Healthcare-associated infections (HAI) constitute one of the most significant challenges to healthcare systems worldwide. These infections, by definition, are acquired during a patient's stay in healthcare institutions and tend to manifest 48 hours after admission or up to 30 days following an intervention¹. The occurrence of HAI is linked to intrinsic patient factors, like advanced age and comorbidities; and extrinsic elements such as utilization of medical devices and different procedures^{2,3}. However, reported incidence rates range from 3% to over 30% depending on the methodology, sample size, and geographical location^{4,5}. Nevertheless, the higher quality data tend to narrow this margin while reporting a significantly high prevalence of 5-10% of all intensive care unit (ICU) pa-

A retrospective analysis was performed to assess HAI prevalence and its relationship with healthcare determinants among intensive care unit (ICU) patients of the José Carrasco Arteaga Hospital in 2019. The sample was represented by the entirety of the clinical records from patients admitted to the ICU during 2019, even after applying both inclusion and exclusion criteria. The inclusion criteria were: Patients hospitalized for at least 48 hours and diagnosed with HAI during their stay. The exclusion criterion was cases with pre-existing infections at the time of admission. A total of 515 patient records were analyzed, including several demographic variables such as age, sex, education level, occupation, length of stay, comorbidities, and the use of medical devices.

Data collection was structured and standardized specifically for this purpose. Variables were categorized as either dependent (HAI) or independent (age, sex, oc-

cupation, level of education, comorbidities, and use of invasive medical devices). The analytical approach included both descriptive statistics and inferential analyses. Measures of association, including prevalence ratios and confidence intervals, were calculated, employing SPSS version 22 and Epi Info for data processing software. Measures of central tendency and dispersion were calculated for age. Moreover, the prevalence ratio was used to estimate association, using 1 as a neutral value, alongside a 95% confidence interval (CI) and a Chi-square (X²) value taken as significant when $p < 0,05$.

The ethical integrity of the research was maintained through strict adherence to confidentiality protocols. Patient data were anonymized and coded, ensuring compliance with institutional and regulatory guidelines while maintaining the privacy rights of the patients uncompromised. Moreover, the database was set to be erased once the investigation was finalized to further protect sensitive information. The author declares no conflict of interest.

had an occupation (59%). Regarding educational level, most of the patients only had a basic level of education (41.4%) while the highest level of education was only achieved by a quarter of the population (25.3%).

The most frequently identified comorbidities were hypertension (HT) (39.8%), diabetes mellitus (DM) (23.5%), and cancer (15.3%), while 47.4% had no significant comorbidities. On the other hand, the most implemented medical devices were mechanical ventilation (38.8%), central venous catheter (CVC) (33.8%), and urinary catheter (27.8%).

There were a total of 79 cases of HAI, with an overall prevalence of 15.3%. Bacterial pathogens were the primary etiological agents, mainly represented by *E. coli* (25.3%) and *K. pneumoniae* (12.7%) within the Gram-negative group; whilst *Staphylococcus spp.* was the leading Gram-positive pathogen (27%). On the other hand, *Candida glabrata* accounted for 2.5% of the cases.

It was also found that the population aged over 50 years, male, residing in urban areas, with low educational level, and with no occupation showed the highest proportion of HAI cases, although none of these subgroups achieved statistical significance ($p > 0.05$). Likewise, no comorbidity seemed to have a significant influence on the incidence of HAI ($p > 0.05$), **Table 1**. However, in-hospital factors showed a significant association with HAI incidence, mainly prolonged hospital stays (≥ 15 days, relative risk [RR]: 4.00, $p < 0.05$) and the use of mechanical ventilation (RR: 1.69, $p = 0.009$), **Table 2**.

Results

The study included 515 patients with a mean age of 56.71 ± 19 years, ranging from 20 to 97. The majority of the population were adults over 61 years (47.4%), with a slight predominance of males (53%) over females (47%). In addition, most of the patients resided in urban areas (70.3%) and more than half

Table 1. Influence of comorbidities in the prevalence of HAI.

COMORBIDITY		POPULATION WITH HAI				RR CI: 95 %	p
		WITH		WITHOUT			
		N	%	N	%		
HT	YES	39	19.0	166	81.0	1.474 0.984-2.208	0.05
	NO	40	12.9	270	87.1		
DIABETES	YES	12	9.9	109	90.1	0.583 0.326-1.041	0.05
	NO	67	17.0	327	83.0		
CANCER	YES	10	12.7	69	87.3	0.799 0.431- 1.484	0.472
	NO	69	15.8	367	84.2		
TRAUMA	YES	2	14.3	12	85.7	0.925 0.253-3.408	0.911
	NO	77	15.4	424	85.6		
COPD	YES	4	30.8	9	69.2	2.059 0.887-4.778	0.117
	NO	75	14.9	427	85.1		
HIV	YES	1	7.7	12	92.3	0.495 0.074-3.290	0.438
	NO	78	15.5	424	85.8		

HT: Hypertension, COPD: Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease, HIV: Human Immunodeficiency Virus, HAI: Healthcare-associated Infections

Table 2. Influence of intrahospital factors (medical devices and length of hospitalization) in the prevalence of HAI.

INTRAHOSPITALARY FACTORS			POPULATION WITH HAI				RR 95 %	p
			WITH		WITHOUT			
			N	%	N	%		
Central Venous Catheter	Yes		26	14.9	148	85.1	0.961 0.624 – 1.481	0.858
	No		53	15.5	288	84.5		
Urinary Catheter	Yes		29	20.3	114	79.7	1.508 0.996- 2.284	0.05
	No		50	13.4	322	86.6		
Tracheostomy	Yes		5	17.9	23	82.1	1.175 0.516- 2.672	0.703
	No		74	15.2	413	84.8		
Mechanical Ventilation	Yes		41	20.5	159	79.5	1.699 1.134- 2.545	0.009
	No		38	12.1	277	87.9		
	No		13	9.0	131	91.0		
Length of stay	15 - 36 days		11	55.0	9	45.0	4.003 2.54- 6.302	0.001
	3 - 14 days		68	13.7	427	86.3		

HAI: Healthcare-associated Infections.

Discussion

HAI remain a pressing challenge within hospital environments, especially in the ICU setting where patients are exposed to heightened risks due to invasive procedures and prolonged length of stay. At first glance, the findings from this study align with global trends, where HAI prevalence rates range between 7-10%. Nevertheless, the prevalence of 15.3% reported here reflects the critical burden of HAI in Ecuador's healthcare context and highlights the need for targeted interventions mainly focused on preventive measures, along with standardized management protocols to decrease HAI morbidity and mortality.

Although statistical analysis reported a higher incidence in the males, subjects aged over 50 years, urban residents, those with an occupation, and those at least one comorbidity; no significant association was found between these variables and the incidence of HAI. In contrast, a significant association was found between HAI and mechanical ventilation (RR: 1.69. $p=0.009$); as well as with prolonged hospital stay, especially over 15 days (≥ 15 days, relative risk [RR]: 4.00, $p < 0.05$), as shown in **Table 2**.

Conversely, Álvares et al.¹¹ found that usage of CVC, urinary catheter, orotracheal intubation, and need for mechanical ventilation had similar risk profiles regarding HAI incidence. The reported OR were 4.7, 3.5, and 7.01 for CVC, urinary catheter, and mechanical ventilation, respectively. Indeed, Salmanov et al.¹² reported that over 47% of the patients with HAI also had a CVC, although no analysis for correlation was performed, only the association was mentioned.

In this study, HAI incidence was found to be unaffected by comorbidities such as HT, DM, and cancer given that the prevalence of these pathologies tends to increase with age, making them relatively common within the analyzed groups as shown in **Table 1**¹³. However, despite

not increasing the incidence ratio of HAI, other studies have reported that decompensated comorbidities tend to influence negative outcomes in general, especially mortality, length of stay, and need for rehospitalization¹⁴⁻¹⁶. All things considered, comorbidities could indirectly influence the incidence of HAI through increased length of stay and rehospitalizations, although those variables were not assessed during this investigation. In this regard, Vilca et al.¹⁷ found that having at least one comorbidity resulted in an odds ratio (OR) of 2.84 in contrast to no comorbidities.

In our analysis, the most frequently isolated bacteria were *E. coli* 25.3% and *K. pneumoniae* 12.7% (Gram-negative) and *Staphylococcus spp.* 27.9% (Gram-positive). Previously, Escobar et al.¹⁸ reported that the most frequent causative agent of HAI was *Acinetobacter baumannii* (21%), with Gram-positive agents being more prevalent than Gram-negative bacteria. Similarly, Despotovic et al.⁵ reported *E. coli* to be the causative agent in 29% of the population, followed by *P. aeruginosa* at 17%; whereas Montúfar-Andrade et al.¹⁹ found the main isolated organism to be *S. aureus* (28%). These discrepancies highlight the need for local microbiological surveillance to adapt empiric treatment protocols to the local reality.

In ensemble, the aforementioned data sheds light on the relevance of analyzing the in-hospital setting for future improvement in our setting, given the environmental variables showed the highest relevance concerning HAI incidence. While analyzing sociodemographic variables seems important to understand the heterogeneous context of HAI occurrence, most of the available information has shown no significant contribution. In conclusion, addressing HAI requires a multifaceted approach, combining solid infection prevention measures, ongoing surveillance, and targeted strategies for the education of healthcare providers. Thus, by implementing evidence-

based interventions in the ICU setting, hospitals can mitigate both the epidemiological and financial burden of HAI while also improving patient outcomes.

Conclusions

Understanding the prevalence of a condition as well as the surrounding this epidemiologic outlook is primordial to elaborate proper resolutive strategies. Through this study, a prevalence of HAI of 15.3% was observed in an ICU setting. Moreover, a bacteriological profile brought to light the most frequent causative agents of this condition, enabling the ability to establish local treatment protocols targeted toward said pathogens. Additionally, prolonged hospitalizations and the use of medical devices were heavily associated with HAI. As a recommendation, minimizing the time for antibiogram results could improve the time for selection of proper antibiotics, resulting in less antibiotic resistance and shorter length of stay. Likewise, personnel capacitation is needed for proper management of medical devices to further decrease the incidence of HAI. However, the need for epidemiological surveillance remains as the implemented strategies need to be evaluated in the future to assess their efficacy.

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